

THE VIEWS OF PUPIL ON TEACHER UNDESIRABLE BEHAVIORS IN THEIR APPRENTICESHIP PROGRAM

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Abstract

At the beginning, it is found in most of the countries that offer teacher education are not concerned with the current need and development needed for the school and the industry (real life), rather they just design the curriculum as per the decision of members of the board or senate. Generally, the board does not want to discuss exactly with the nominees or experienced teachers and the school manager. Results are in a big gap for the education operators especially, nominee teachers, too. Preparing a suitable training program and job ready teachers we need nominee teacher perceptions on their trainers and teacher. In this content, in an undesirable environment for pupils' perceptions are very essential. Undesirable environment for practice is defined as the environment that has behavior which is not suitable for the situation or the environment, but it is acted consciously in it. In this study, it is aimed to determine the views of the pupil on teacher undesirable behaviors in their apprenticeship program. The population of this research is 370 students who study in NEÜ Education faculty 7th-semester

students in the academic year 2017-2018 in Konya. This paper that tries to find the ways on the grounds for synergetic partnerships between the faculty of education and industry for a win-win situation for both the sides revealed that pupil perceptions are ranged in two groups between “strongly disagree” with the interval 1.00-1.80 and “disagree” with the interval 1.81-2.60.

Keywords: faculty of education-school collaboration, theory and practice, partnership, student perceptions, Undesirable environment

1. Introduction

In Turkey, Faculties of educations were established with the restructuring in 1982. To minimize problems associated with teacher training, faculties of education classified their teacher training programs in two groups as "elementary school teacher" and "the teacher of secondary education". Each teacher training program has courses with proportions of, the professional knowledge and skills of 50-60%, 25-30% of the pedagogical knowledge and skills, 15-20% of the general culture. After completing courses on professional and pedagogical knowledge and skills, all pupils in schools have to join a one-semester internship/application program (Demirel and Kaya, 2012).

In Turkey, the Turkish Science and Technology Institute (TÜBİTAK), in its recommendations to the nation before a couple of years has advocated for the establishment of synergy between teacher education and creativity. (Tübitak, 2013). The most important thing in creative education is that it has to be should be supported by an invoking environment in which the mind power has to tie up with the networking power in the schools facilitates sufficient opportunities for the pioneering brains of the young creative teacher nominee students.

Undesirable environment for practice is defined as the environment that has behavior which is not suitable for the situation or the environment, but it is acted consciously in it. According to that definition, all environments that have behaviors which interfere with the educational efforts in schools and stajs can be characterized as inappropriate behavior (Sağlam et al, 2007). While mentioning about inappropriate behaviors encountered in educational environments, the first thought is the inappropriate behavior of students. However, teachers might show different inappropriate behaviors and those behaviors could lead to negative consequences on learning and behavior of students (Bonfield 2003; Dolin 1995; Toale 2001). At the same time, those behaviors decrease total self-confidence and learning skills of them. Particularly, the undesirable behavior of teacher among the inappropriate educational environment prevents student learning and their creativities either directly or indirectly (Kearney et al. 1991).

“Undesirable behavior” is defined as defamatory behaviors of the teacher on students such as using derogatory language, embarrassing or insulting student within his colleagues and verbal harassment to students by using inappropriate language. The verbal undesirable behavior of teacher reduces the student to develop a positive attitude toward learning so that behavior prevents the learning of students and it creates hostile emotions on students against learning subjects (Bekiari et al. 2005). Some surveys conducted by Gözütok (1993), Memişoğlu (2005), Tor and Sargın (2005), Cobanoglu and Senturk (2005) showed that 30% of the teachers are working to ensure discipline in the class by showing the behaviors that could be characterized as negative behaviors (hair pulling, slapping, insulting, threading by class mark, taking student to the principal or throwing chalk). Maurer and Wallerstein (1984) statistically investigated the effects of teacher’s negative behavior on learning. They examined the relationship between failure and the negative attitude of the teacher in 50 public

high schools and they concluded that increasing the negativity of teacher's behavior decreases the success of students.

Students want to be valued by teachers in educational environments and to be treated carefully. Students expect directed interest, curiosity, and anxiety on them. from their teachers beyond academic support. If the teacher is perceived as a person that is interested in students personally, the student gets the higher motivation to participate in class activities or toward learning (Phelan, Davidson and Cao 1992).

It is important for the student whether the teacher-student relationship is healthy or not. A conducted research showed that the learning aspiration of students is negatively affected by teachers who cared neither students nor their study (Phelan, Davidson and Cao, 1992). Additionally; in Sheets' study (2002), students complained that teachers did not listen to them, they did not make any effort to communicate with students and there were no friendly relations between students and teachers.

The educational environment is not only a place where learning-teaching activities maintained but also it is a place in which student develops a self-perception and their creativity by interacting with his teacher and friends. Also according to Açıkgöz (2005), teacher as a person that has the most intimate and long-term interaction with students, should undertake functions such as being a role model and making guidance to the student in addition to his main function of "learning facilitation". It is not possible to talk about the quality of the education system and industry collaboration in the absence of a qualified teacher. Therefore, this study aims to determine the views of the pupils on the undesirable behavior of teachers in their apprenticeship.

1.1. The Purpose of the Study

In this study, it is aimed to determine the views of the pupil on teacher undesirable behaviors in their apprenticeship. For synergetic partnerships between the faculty of education and industry for a win-win situation for both the sides and progressing education program, the question that “According to pupil’s perceptions, in what extent their teachers show undesirable teacher behaviors?” is determined as the problem sentences.

2. Method

This research tries to determine the views of the pupil on the undesirable behaviors of the teacher. This study is descriptive research since it is aimed to state directly the existing conditions on the issue and the general scanning model was used among the scanning models in this research. Scanning models are the research approaches that aim to describe a situation which happened in the past or still exist with its all contents (Karasar, 1995).

2.1. Sample of the Population

The population of this research is students who study in NEÜ Education faculty 7th-semester students in the academic year 2017-2018 in Konya. It is not possible to access the entire population of the pupil so sample selection was applied by using asymmetrical selection model. Because 370 students filled the questionnaire as requested and the sample of the population was comprised of 430 students.

2.2. Data collection tool

In the study, “Undesirable Teacher Behavior Scale” developed by Erben Keçici, S., Beyhan, Ö. & Sönmez Ektem, I. (2013, a) was used as a data collection

tool. The scale is Likert-type scale and has 22 questions in the first factor that is “undesirable behaviors of teacher” (Table1). The scale KMO value is 0.923 and Bartlett sphericity test result is also significant for [$\chi^2=7229/sd=703, p<0.000$] found (Scherer, 1988). The eigenvalue of factor analysis be taken 3.00 and two factors, eigenvalue larger than 3.00, were determined (Büyüköztürk, 2002). There are significant ($p<0.01$) middle level positive linear relationship($r =.642$) between scale factors. Each dimension Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of the scale are 0.91 and 0.92. Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient is 0.94(Kline, 1994). Confirmatory factor analysis χ^2/sd rate is 2.52. GFI value is 0.79, AGFI value is 0.76, RMSEA value is 0.06, CFI value is 0.85, NFI value is 0.78 and PGFI value is 0.69, respectively. The scale of the data in perfect harmony with the values, even if not acceptable limits (Jorokog & Sorbom, 1993; Brown, 2006).

After Applying the scale, the ordinal scale was used for data analyses. Each range coefficient for five options scale is (4/5) 0.80. 1.00-1.80 ranges represent “strongly disagree”, 1.81 - 2.60 ranges represent “disagree”, 2.61-3.40 ranges represent “neutral”, 3.41-4.20 ranges represent “agree” and 4.21-5.00 ranges represent I “totally agree”.

2.3. Analysis of the data

The data were computerized and analyzed by using SPSS 25 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) computer program. The arithmetic means and standard deviations of views of students on undesirable behavior of teacher were determined

3. Results

The problem sentence is that “according to pupil’s perceptions, to what extent their teachers show undesirable teacher behavior?” In table 1, according to pupil’s perceptions, undesirable teacher behaviors on those issues are listed depending on mean values and standard deviations. When table1 is analyzed, it is seen that the grading scale of students’ views is ranged in two groups between “strongly disagree” with the interval 1.00-1.80 and “disagree” with the interval 1.81-2.60.

Table 1. The statistical data on undesirable behaviors of teacher.

	The inappropriate behavior of teacher	N	Average	Std. Dev.
1.	<i>He/she thought that I was not suitable for the school.</i>	370	1,84	1,349
2.	He/she used to say that I was psychologically ill.	370	1,56	1,069
3.	<i>He used to say that I did not have adequate reasoning ability.</i>	370	1,82	1,264
4.	<i>He/she would mock my failures or mistakes in the lesson.</i>	370	2,05	1,430
5.	<i>She used to mock my outer appearance (A physical characteristic)</i>	370	2,09	1,437
6.	He/she used to mock my name.	370	1,75	1,257
7.	To exclude me from class activities, he/she used to assign tasks that were impossible for me to do.	370	1,59	1,106
8.	He/she used to behave as if I did not exist.	370	1,61	1,088
9.	<i>He/she constantly interrupted me and did not allow me to speak.</i>	370	1,91	1,302
10.	<i>When I raised my finger to get a permission to speak, he/she did not use to let me.</i>	370	1,99	1,350
11.	<i>Whenever I wanted to talk to him/her, he/she avoided speaking to me by making up an excuse.</i>	370	2,04	1,331
12.	He/she intentionally kept me waiting for a long time.	370	1,75	1,157
13.	<i>He/she used to say negative things about me when I was absent.</i>	370	1,86	1,252

14.	<i>He/she used to reveal things related to my private life.</i>	370	1,98	1,441
15.	<i>He/she used to attack my private life.</i>	370	1,83	1,330
16.	<i>He/she used to tell the principal and other teachers negative things about me.</i>	370	1,83	1,299
17.	He/she used to tell my family negative things about me.	370	1,80	1,255
18.	<i>He/she used to send me to the principal even in the case of the smallest problem.</i>	370	1,90	1,337
19.	He/she used to criticize my works and homework.	370	1,77	1,240
20.	<i>He/she used to give bad marks without informing me about the reason.</i>	370	2,15	1,418
21.	<i>He/she used to give punishments arbitrarily</i>	370	2,09	1,394
22.	<i>He/she used to shout, insult and curse for no reason.</i>	370	2,17	1,447

Students give their opinions as “strongly disagree” for the following questions (second, sixth, seventh, 12th and 17th) with the highest given arithmetical average values(1,80) “He/she used to tell my family negative things about me” and the lowest given arithmetical average values (1,56) “He/she used to say that I was psychologically ill”.

Students give their opinions as “disagree” for the questions in italics in table1 with the highest given arithmetical average values (2,17) “He/she used to shout, insult and curse for no reason.” And the lowest (1,83) “He used to say that I did not have adequate reasoning ability”.

4. Discussion

Undesirable behavior problems do not occur alone, when the problems of undesirable behavior in the classroom are understood, the reason for the formation of inappropriate behavior problems can be identified. To correct those problems not only the target students’ behaviors but also the teachers’ behavior must be taken into consideration.

For synergetic partnerships between the faculty of education and industry for which use teachers graduate from it a win-win situation for both the sides education faculty needs enough datum for progressing education program. The more information we have about the creative and suitable education environment the more educated and ready teacher for real conditions.

There are not many kinds of research on that issue in our country. While talking about inappropriate or undesirable behaviors, mostly student aggression is the focus point. This research is important in this regard since we tried to investigate the effects of inappropriate teachers' behaviors on students.

This study was conducted on pupil .in their apprenticeship program. The results show that in the extent of the question "According to pupils' perceptions, to what extent their teachers show undesirable teacher behavior?", the findings were not much high statistically. The effects of undesirable teachers' behavior could be high even if the action is repeated rarely. For example, the study of Dolin (1995) supports this judgment. Even teacher shows undesirable behaviors rarely, those effect students in a negative way such as decreasing the participation to the in-class activities, decreasing the desire of learning and decreasing to behave in an appropriate way. This type of behaviors negatively affects cognitive and effective learning of students and they increase the resistance of the negative behaviors of students.

The results obtained in this research are not consistent with the result of other research in that field. Many kinds of research tell that teachers could show undesirable behaviors in class and those behaviors lead to negative effects on students' learning and their creativity, and as a result of the undesirable behavior of teachers, the students show undesirable (Dolin 1995; Toale 2001). Undesirable teacher behavior is one of the reasons that affect learning and in-class behaviors of student unfavorably. Besides, it is stated that that kind of behaviors is

performed commonly among teachers (Memişođlu 2005, Roberson and Doebler 200, Sheets 2002, Bekiari et al. 2005, Bulu 2006). The reason of not to get a similar result with previous studies in this study can be concluded that high school (or elementary school) students could be under the influence of the events of this period more than the adult students in university or college. The reason for encountering more cases in this period might be results of contradictions between adolescence period of students and authoritarian conceptions of the teacher.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The Undesirable behaviors in the education environment should not be overstated and the teacher should avoid hardcore reactions. The Undesirable experiences in class cause students to develop a negative attitude toward school and teachers so that triggers the failure of students. At the same time, undesirable behaviors kill students' creativity.

The teacher training institutions should consider those cases and institutions should add similar case studies to their curriculum to give different examples to teacher candidates. If teacher candidates have enough information about situations encountered in class, they will be prepared for the situations and so better decisions on class management can be applied.

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